

Can Access to Remittance Improve Livelihood Diversification and Poverty in Nigeria?

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Abstract

Poverty is a major challenge faced by many households in Nigeria, which is a result of inadequate income to cater for household needs. As a source of additional income, remittance helps fulfil the purpose of catering to needs. It serves as a source that enhances livelihood diversification to generate more income. The study's general objective was to determine the effect of remittance on livelihood diversification and poverty. The study was carried out in the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Secondary data collected from General Household Survey data, 2015 were used. The data collected were analysed using the Simpson index, Logit regression model, Foster-Greer-Thorbecke (FGT), and Tobit regression model. Remittance, Gender, Age, Marital Status, Household size, Farm size, and Distance to market significantly influenced livelihood diversification. Poverty was influenced by Gender, Marital Status (married), Years of formal education, household size, Farm size, occupation, and access to credit. Remittance was not found to significantly influence poverty because only a few had access to it. Remittance access should be improved as increased access and a greater proportion of remittance in the study area would significantly increase livelihood diversification and indirectly reduce poverty.

Keywords: Foster-Greer-Thorbecke (FGT), Livelihood diversification, Nigeria, Poverty, Remittance, Simpson Index.

1 Introduction

Poverty remains a major problem in most developing countries, and Nigeria continues to be one of the poorest despite efforts by the government to reduce the incidence of poverty through poverty alleviation programmes and its quest to become one of the largest economies (Adepoju, 2012). World Bank reports that Nigeria faces extreme cases of poverty. In Nigeria, 40.1 per cent (82.9 million) are below the poverty line of 137430 naira per capita in consumption expenditure, implying that 4 out of every Nigerian is poor (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

However, agriculture is the mainstay of Nigeria's economy, employing about 70 per cent of the population. Agricultural activities are by nature prone to various risks, shocks and uncertainties, which can be biotic such as pest and disease), environmental such as drought) or economical in case of shortage of funds (Gitz & Meybeck, 2012). The average impact of the shock on household welfare is persistent; uninsured risks and shocks are likely to have a persistent impact on household welfare and growth, especially for poorer

households (Dercon, 2004). It may thus contribute to poverty persistence due to a reduction in the productivity of the households. Low productivity in the sector has been associated with the fact that the agriculture sector mostly comprises small-scale farmers who still use rudimentary production techniques, making them highly dependent on manual labour. Agricultural productivity growth effectively reduces poverty by generating income for poor farmers. The unavailability of funds to carry out timely purchases of cash inputs into agricultural production, as well as to buy capital equipment like ploughs or water pumps, has long been regarded as one of the critical constraints inhibiting rising productivity in small-farm agriculture (Mgbenka *et al.*, 2015).

Livelihood diversification as a strategy for reducing poverty among households provides alternative methods of income generation apart from the main source of income. Losch *et al.* (2010) defined livelihood diversification as both on-farm and off-farm economic activities undertaken to generate additional

income other than those generated mainly from agricultural activities. Despite the numerous benefits of livelihood diversification, poverty hinders livelihood diversification amongst households. Herein, poverty arises from insufficient income and other resources the household needs to expand their economic activities; often, it results in malnutrition, general weakness, proliferation of sickness and disease and eventual death. In addition, it results in a massive reduction in people's productivity both at the individual and national levels (Mgbenka *et al.*, 2015). Hence, households have evolved various means to cope with the menace of poverty by diversifying into non-farm ventures. Engaging in diverse livelihood activities can be enhanced with remittance, hence, reducing poverty.

Remittance helps developing countries lower poverty, increase savings and investment as a means of augmenting consumption, and improve human capital. Remittances are all cash or kind transfers sent or brought from non-residents to resident households. Remittance greatly reduces rural poverty by financing health and education and easing credit constraints for small businesses. It serves as a source of insurance during natural calamities and human-induced shocks and improves current account sustainability and creditworthiness (Ratha, 2012). Earnings from remittances can strengthen livelihoods through investment in land or land improvements, purchase of cash inputs to agriculture, investment in agricultural implements or machines, education, and in assets permitting local non-farm income to be generated. It can be seen as a part of wider resilience and livelihood strategies and broader concepts of kinship and reciprocity as a part of informal insurance and networking processes (Khadkha, 2015).

Increased access to remittance can improve farmers' risk-bearing ability and productivity, encouraging involvement in diverse livelihood activities. The reasons behind the diversification of livelihood activities include diminishing returns from increasing investment in certain activities, lack of or unstable markets to minimise, cope with, and spread risk, creating consumption and labour smoothing, and adapting to income challenges over time (Ellis, 2003). Livelihood diversification's contribution to rural livelihoods is significant and has often been ignored by policymakers who have chosen to focus their activities on agriculture (Ellis, 1998). Due to the prevalence of risk and market failure in rural economies of low-income developing countries, consumption smoothing is a real difficulty for the household, made more acute the nearer the household is to bare survival livelihood circumstances and the higher the risks attached to the uneven income sources on which it depends (Lipton & Ravallion, 1995). An important motive for income diversification associated with seasonality is to reduce seasonal income variability. This requires income-earning opportunities that are not synchronised with the

farm's seasons. Remittance, therefore, becomes useful as a source of income diversification for eradicating poverty.

Although Nigeria is a high remittance-receiving country, there is evidence in the literature pointing to the increasing poverty and income inequality level in Nigeria over the last two decades (Olowa *et al.*, 2013). The increasing amount of remittance in Nigeria from \$2.3 billion in 2004 to \$20.9 billion in 2022 (*World Bank Open Data*, 2023a) has, therefore, been unable to reduce poverty in Nigeria, which is also increasing. The Nigerian government has enacted several policies and introduced programs to reduce poverty among its people. Despite this, the problem of poverty appeared to be intractable.

Several studies have been carried out on poverty, and none have linked livelihood diversification and remittance to poverty in one study. The tendency for households to engage in multiple occupations is often remarked on, but few attempts have been made to link this behaviour systematically to poverty. This study will, therefore, add to existing knowledge by examining remittance, livelihood diversification, and poverty among households in Nigeria. This study is also crucial because it addresses the first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), which seeks to eradicate poverty in all its forms. The increasing rate of outmigration in Nigeria is presently at -0.21 per 1000 persons (Galal, 2023), indicating that the number of emigrants is higher than those immigrating to the country due to the economic state of the nation which also calls for the examining effect of migrant remittance on the welfare of migrant-receiving households. This study seeks to answer the following research questions in line with the above.

- 1) What is the effect of remittance on livelihood diversification in Nigeria?
- 2) What is the effect of remittance on poverty among households in Nigeria?

2 Literature Review

Several empirical studies have shown that remittance contributes greatly to poverty alleviation. It can alleviate poverty through migrants sending to countries and mitigate adverse shocks' impact. It is seen as a poverty reduction tool with favourable impacts as recipient households of remittance are seen to have reduced poverty substantially (Waheed *et al.*, 2013). Using the switching probit model and ordinary least squares regression, migrant remittance positively and significantly impacted household welfare (Salman, 2016).

Though remittances can be from local, i.e. within the country or international sources, they have differential effects on poverty. Waheed *et al.* (2013) studied the

effects of remittances on poverty among rural households in Nigeria using the Nigerian National Living Standard Survey (NLSS), 2004, to analyse the impact of domestic remittances (from Nigeria) and foreign remittances (from African and other countries) on poverty in rural Nigeria. The Foster, Greer and Thorbecke poverty measures revealed that a 10% increase in domestic remittances decreased Poverty Incidence (PI), Poverty Gap (PG) and Squared Poverty Gap (SPG) by 1.80%, 1.60% and 1.60%. In comparison, a 10% rise in foreign remittances reduced poverty incidence (PI), Poverty gap (PG) and Squared poverty gap (SPG) by 0.86%. However, the positive effect of remittance analysed using the Gini coefficient is useful for people with availability and access to remittance than those without it. Livelihood diversification, also in the form of income diversification, is therefore useful to influence welfare and poverty.

Several factors influence livelihood diversification age, farm size, size of livestock holding, distance to market, and access to rural credit service influence the diversification decision of the farmer (Negeri & Demissie, 2016; Sherf-UI-Alam et al. 2017) while gender, education.62% and 0.62%, respectively, in rural Nigeria. The measures show that including domestic or foreign remittances in household expenditure reduces the level, depth, and severity of poverty in rural Nigeria (Adams and Page, 2005).

Remittance is often insufficient to change a person's condition; hence, there is little dependency on it (Khadkha, 2015). However, the positive effect of remittance analysed using the Gini coefficient is useful for people with availability and access to remittance than those without it. Livelihood diversification, also in the form of income diversification, is therefore useful to influence welfare and poverty.

Several factors influence livelihood diversification age, farm size, size of livestock holding, distance to market, while access to rural credit service influence the diversification decision of the farmer (Negeri & Demissie, 2016; Sherf-UI-Alam et al. 2017). Whereas, gender, education level, marital status, family size, membership status of the sampled farmers, access to credit and market distance does not (Sherf-UI-Alam et al., 2017). Collin's (2016) study revealed that a multitude of factors have a substantial influence on the diversification of income within families. The study revealed that variables such as the number of years of formal education completed by the household head, marital status, and access to both formal and informal credit were associated with a detrimental impact on income diversification. Conversely, it was found that the degree of contentment among rural households about amenities, the gender of the family head, the total value of household savings and assets, and agricultural training were all characteristics that had a beneficial

impact on income diversification. Households residing in diversified regions face a range of primary challenges. These challenges encompass an inadequate asset base, limited access to credit facilities, insufficient awareness and training opportunities, aversion to risk-taking, inadequate rural infrastructure, and limited prospects in the non-farm sector. On the other hand, in regions with lower levels of diversification, the primary limitations are characterised by insufficient transportation infrastructure, a limited asset foundation, unsuitable agro-climatic circumstances, and restricted availability of financial facilities.

Olaleye and Oyinbo (2016), using the Foster, Greer, and Thorbecke poverty model and Tobit regression, opined that a farming household head who engages in several livelihood activities is less likely to be poor. Livelihood activities determined using the Simpson index (Sherf-UI-Alam et al., 2017; Negeri & Demissie, 2016) increase farmers' incomes and, invariably, their purchasing power and welfare.

This study will employ the use of Simpson Index, Foster, Greer and Thorbecke (FGT), Tobit regression model and Logit Model in its analysis employed in literature to determine the effect of remittance on poverty and livelihood diversification, such as the Simpson Index (Sherf-UI-Alam et al., 2017; Khatiwada et al., 2017), Foster, Greer and Thorbecke model to determine poverty status (Oyinbo & Olaleye, 2016; Waheed et al., 2013; Awotide et al., 2010, Logit Model (Sherf-UI-Alam et al., 2017).

2.1 Study area

This study was carried out in Nigeria, a country located in West Africa, encompassing a landmass of 923,768 square kilometres (356,669 square miles). Nigeria is geographically partitioned into thirty-six states and one Federal Capital Territory. These administrative divisions are further delineated into 774 Local Government Areas (LGAs). Nigeria is geographically situated close to several neighbouring countries. To the west, it shares a land border spanning approximately 773 kilometres (480 miles) with the Republic of Benin. In the northeast, Nigeria is bordered by Lake Chad, with a distance of approximately 87 kilometres (54 miles). To the east, the country shares a border of approximately 1,690 kilometres (1,050 miles) with Cameroon. Lastly, in the northern region, Nigeria is bordered by Niger, with a distance of around 1,497 kilometres (930 miles). The country's coastal region is situated along the Gulf of Guinea, spanning at least 853 kilometres (530 miles). Nigeria is geographically situated within the latitudinal range of 4° to 14°N and the longitudinal range of 2° to 15°E. Nigeria encompasses several noteworthy geological features, such as the Adamawa highlands, Mambilla Plateau, Jos Plateau, Obudu Plateau, the Niger River, River Benue, and Niger Delta (Ajayi et al., 2024).

Nigeria is called the "Giant of Africa" due to its substantial population and robust economy. Nigeria, boasting a population of over 200 million individuals (Sasu, 2024), is the most populous nation on the African continent and is projected to be 5th largest country globally in terms of population by 2050 (UNICEF, 2023). Nigeria is the 30th largest economy globally, with a monetary value of about \$477 billion and \$1.28 trillion in nominal GDP and purchasing power parity (*World Bank Open Data*, 2023b)

Nevertheless, the country's current Human Development index (HDI) is low, placing it at 163rd in global rankings (UNDP, 2022).

2.2 Data

The study utilised the 2015 General Household Survey (GHS) data collected by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (*General Household Survey 2016*, 2024). The GHS-Panel component for Nigeria is part of a wider regional effort in Sub-Saharan Africa to enhance agricultural statistics. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMA&RD), the National Food Reserve Agency (NFRA), the World Bank (WB), and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) collaborated to produce the statistics.

The GHS-Panel's goals include creating a cutting-edge model for gathering agricultural data, inter-institutional cooperation, and thorough analysis of welfare indicators and socioeconomic traits. The GHS-Panel is a 5,000-household survey that is representative of all households and the geopolitical zones (both urban and rural). A subset of the total number of GHS sample households comprises the GHS panel. The General Household Survey employed a multi-stage stratified sample design. The GHS sample consists of 60 Enumeration Areas (EAs), or Primary Sampling Units (PSUs), picked from each of Nigeria's 37 states for 2220 EAs nationwide. This study used 1647 households spread across all states and regions. Information was collected on remittance, livelihood diversification and household socioeconomic characteristics such as household size, age, gender, marital status, years of farming experience and educational level of household head, amongst others.

3 Methodology

3.1 Simpson Index

The diversification index will be measured with the help of the Simpson index of diversity. The Simpson index of diversity is defined as expressed in Equation (1):

$$SID = 1 - \sum_i P_i^2 \quad (1)$$

Where P_i is the proportion of income coming from source i , the value of SID always falls between 0 and 1. If there is just one source of income, $P_i=1$, so $SID=0$. As the number of sources increases, the shares (P_i) decline, as does the sum of the squared shares, so SID approaches 1. If there are k sources of income, then SID falls between zero and $1-1/k$.

Accordingly, households with the most diversified incomes will have the largest SID and the less diversified incomes are associated with the smallest SID. For least diversified households (i.e., those depending on a single income source), SID takes on its minimum value of 0. The upper limit for SID is 1, depending on the available income sources and their relative shares. SID increases with the number of income sources and increasing even distribution of income shares. The Simpson Index of Diversity is affected by the number of income sources and income distribution between the different sources (balance). The more uniformly distributed the income from each source, the SID approaches to 1.

3.2 Foster, Greer, Thorbecke (FGT) Poverty Measure

FGT with P_α class of poverty indices will be used to determine the poverty level among households in the study area. Following the notation of Foster, Greer and Thorbecke (FGT) (1984) and Taylor *et al.* (2005), FGT is specified as expressed in Equation 2;

$$P_\alpha = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\frac{z-y_i}{z}\right)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

$z > 0$ denotes the predetermined poverty line.

n = the total number of households,

q = is the number of poor households and

α = degree of poverty aversion

The normalised gap $g_i = (z-y_i)/z$ of a poor person i , which is the income deficit stated as a share of the poverty line, serves as the foundation for the FGT class. P is the average level of poverty in the given population, where g_i is the measure of individual poverty for a poor person, and 0 is the corresponding measure for non-poor people. The average for the entire population is just the headcount ratio P_0 or H in the situation when 0 equals the number of poor people, which results in a distribution of individual poverty levels, with each poor person having a poverty level of 1. Case = 1 distinguishes between the poor by using the normalised gap g_i as a measure of poverty level; the average becomes the poverty gap measure P_1 or HI . The normalised gap is squared in the case = 2, which weights gaps by gaps and produces the squared gap measure, P_2 . The state of the poorest impoverished is

all that matters, as goes to infinity. The parameter can be interpreted as a "poverty aversion" indication for someone whose normalised gap is double their poverty level. In contrast, is the elasticity of individual poverty to the normalised gap, meaning that an increase of 1% in a poor person's gap results in an increase of % in that person's poverty level.

4 Econometric Model

4.1 Tobit Regression Model

Tobit regression (Equation 3) will be used to analyse the effect of remittance on livelihood diversification. The use of Tobit model is conceptually preferable parameter estimates from Tobit model overcome most weaknesses of linear probability models namely: providing estimates which are asymptotically consistent and efficient (McDonald and Moffit, 1980). This would therefore be used to get a good fit for our regression as used by Olaleye & Oyinbo (2016) and Dubois & Fattore (2011).

$$L^* = \alpha R + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

Where;

L^* represents the latent variable representing livelihood diversification

α represents the constant term

R represents the remittance access = $\begin{cases} 1; & \text{Access } R > 0 \\ 0; & \text{No access} \end{cases}$ otherwise

β_i represents the slopes

X_i represents the control variables;

ε_i represents the error term assumed to have zero means and constant variance.

4.2 Logit Regression Model

This is used because the dependent variable poverty status takes binary form, and various variables' effects are examined. It is shown in equation 4;

$$P = \alpha R + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (4)$$

Where;

P represents the poverty status = $\begin{cases} 1; & \text{Poor } P > 0 \\ 0; & \text{Non - poor} \end{cases}$ otherwise

α represents the constant term

R represents the remittance access = $\begin{cases} 1; & \text{Access } R > 0 \\ 0; & \text{No access} \end{cases}$ otherwise

β_i represents the slopes

X_i represents the control variables;

ε_i represents the error term assumed to have zero means and constant variance.

The control variables used in the models are described in Table 1 and Appendix 1 shows the distribution.

Table 1: Description of Variables (Household head)

SN	Variable	Description	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Age	Age of household head	50	13.76
2	Household size	Number of household members	7	3.57
3	Farm size	Size of farm in hectares	0.46	0.54
5	Income	Income earned annually	78117.36	85978.34
			Mode (Majority)	
6	Education	Educational attainment of the household head	Primary education	
7	Sex	Sex of the household head	Male	
8	Marital Status	Marital status of the household head; Married or Unmarried(single, divorced, widowed, separated)	Married	
9	Credit access	Access to credit facilities	No Access	
	Member of cooperative	Members of association	Non-member	

5 Results and Discussions

5.1 Remittance and Livelihood Diversification

The results from data showed that only a few (21.07%) respondents, received remittance while a larger number, (78.93%), did not. This gives an advantage to those who received as they have an additional source of income, which can be ploughed into various livelihood activities, thereby increasing income, profit, and poverty.

The Simpson index used to determine the level of diversification showed that the average diversification among households in the study area was 0.78. The highest diversification index was 0.99, while the lowest index was 0.33, with a standard deviation of 0.30. The mean diversification reveals that the level of diversification is very high; this will help increase the household income and drastically reduce poverty among the households. Appendix 2 shows the

distribution of livelihood diversification by the socioeconomic characteristics and poverty status.

5.1.1 Effect of Remittance on Livelihood Diversification

The effect of remittance on livelihood diversification analysed using the Tobit regression model, as shown in Table 2, revealed that households receiving remittance will increase their diversification by 3.5%. This could be because remittance as a source of income diversification generates extra income, which can be ploughed into various activities. This agrees with Khadka (2015), who estimated the sustainable livelihood strategy of remittance for rural Nepal families. He found that the influence on households with and without remittance had positive and negative effects, the positive effect being more useful for people in the community with remittances available.

However, other factors influencing livelihood diversification include sex, age, marital status, household size, farm size and distance to market. This is in unison with Negeri and Demisse (2016), who found that the probability of having a highly diversified livelihood category is affected positively and significantly by the respondent's gender. Age is often assumed to be a major determinant of farmers' agility and ability to diversify their source of income. Young farmers diversify more than their older counterparts due to their strength. Livelihood diversification decreased by 0.2% with an increase in the age of the household head. This may be due to reduced agility, which leads to fewer activities engaged. This agrees with Khatiwada *et al.* (2017) and Negeri & Demissie (2016), who analysed livelihood diversification status, challenges and factors influencing pastoral household's engagement in livelihood diversification activities in six peasant associations selected from two districts in Bale pastoral livelihood zone, Ethiopia. They indicated that factors such as age and education level of household head, size of livestock holding, distance to market and access to rural credit service were the major determinants of livelihood diversification, i.e. the variables are significant.

Unmarried household heads will have their diversification unit decreased compared to household heads that are married. This implies that the livelihood diversification of married households will increase with increased remittance due to the pooling of resources from partners. Household size will increase livelihood diversification probably due to increased labour size for livelihood activities, agreeing with Olumba & Onunka & Onunka (2017). Increase in farm size also increases livelihood diversification by 2.7%. This could be because a larger expanse of farmland provides the opportunity to go into many activities, according to Negeri & Demissie (2016) and Sherf-Ul-Alam *et al.* (2017) thereby increasing livelihood diversification.

They found that farm size and farm holding are significant and positively influence diversification while increase in the farm's distance to the market will decrease livelihood diversification.

Table 2: Tobit Regression Model

Diversification Index	Coefficient (Standard Error)	T	P value	Marginal Effect
Remittance	0.035(0.018)**	1.94	0.052	0.035
Sex (Female)	0.096(0.031)*	3.09	0.002	0.096
Age	-0.003 (0.001)*	-4.22	0.000	-0.002
Marital status (married)	-0.117(0.026)*	-4.42	0.000	-0.116
Education Secondary	0.005(0.019)	0.28	0.778	0.005
Tertiary	-0.014(0.018)	-0.76	0.446	-0.0135
Household size	0.011(0.002)*	4.82	0.000	0.011
Farm size (Ha)	0.027(0.014)**	1.99	0.047	0.027
Distance to market	-0.001(0.0002)*	-3.06	0.002	-0.001
Access to credit	0.005 (0.019)	0.28	0.779	0.005
Member of cooperative	0.035(0.038)	0.91	0.361	0.035
Constant	0.852(0.043)	19.78	0.000	
Sigma	0.292(0.005)			
LR chi ² (11)	=	93.4100		
Pseudo R ²	=	0.1317		
Log-likelihood	=	-307.9376		

*, **, *** signifies 1%, 5%, 10%, respectively.

5.2 Remittance and Poverty Status

The United Nations defines absolute poverty as severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, clothing, shelter, safe drinking water, sanitation facilities, health, information, a safe environment, and social inclusion. Table 3 shows that the poverty gap, which is the average distance by which the mean of income falls below the poverty line, is 67.40%; the poverty incidence, which is the share of the population living below the poverty line, is 56.28% the poverty depth, which is how far below the poverty line does the average poor household income fall is 28.14%, and the poverty severity which response to changes in income distribution among the poor is 46.71% 56.28% of the respondents are poor, while 43.72% are not poor.

Table 3: Poverty Status Distribution of Households

Poverty status	Percentage (%)
Poor	56.28
Non-poor	43.72
Poverty Incidence = 0.5628	
Poverty Depth = -0.2814	
Poverty Severity = 0.4671	
Poverty Gap = 6740.42	

5.2.1 Effect of Remittance on Poverty among the Households

The results of the logit regression model, as shown in Table 4, show an insignificant effect of remittance on poverty among households in Nigeria (P-value is not significant). This implies that remittance does not affect poverty. It could be because a larger percentage of the respondents do not receive remittance, or remittance has not been sufficient to alleviate poverty. The empirical evidence of remittance's positive or negative impacts is inconclusive but points to an intricate set of mixed influences (Waheed *et al.*, 2015).

However, some other variables influenced poverty, such as sex. Households headed by females increase poverty compared to male-headed households. This could be because males are more energetic than females; they cultivate a larger expanse of land than females, yielding higher income, thus reducing poverty than in female-headed households. It agrees with Amaza *et al.* (2009) that male-headed households are also less likely to be poor than female-headed households. Households that are married will have their poverty decreased compared to unmarried households. This could be because of more people available to work to generate income. It also agrees with Amaza *et al.* (2009) that the supply of agricultural family labour can explain the significance of marital status on agricultural production.

The size of farming households increases the probability of a household being poor, in line with the findings of Olaleye & Oyinbo (2016), which state that the coefficient of household size shows a positive relationship with the risk of being poor. This also agrees with the findings of Awotide *et al.* (2010) on poverty and rural livelihood diversification among farming households in southwest Nigeria. In contrast, an increase in farm size will decrease poverty due to more output and yield as farm size increases, creating more food for consumption and higher income to cater for needs, all translating to reduced poverty. Increasing the number of occupations households engage in also reduces poverty. This could result from increased livelihood activities generating various income sources that cater to the household's needs, thereby reducing poverty. Poverty is reduced as more people have access

to credit, and this could be because access to credit enhances access to improved seeds and technology, improved productivity, and greater income aligning with finding from Nosiru (2010), which states that microcredits improve productivity and contribute to increased output, thereby reducing poverty.

Table 4: Logit Regression Model

Poverty status	Coefficient (Standard error)	Z	P value	Marginal Effect
Remittance	0.239(0.206)	1.16	0.246	0.145
Sex(female)	0.7259(0.253)*	2.87	0.004	0.263
Age	-0.0002(0.024)	0.01	0.994	0.011
Married	-0.951(0.013)*	6.750	0.000	-0.121
Years of formal education	0.085(0.012)*	7.79	0.000	0.024
Access to credit	0.219(0.132)***	-1.65	0.098	0.009
Occupation	-0.308(0.111)*	-2.78	0.005	0.020
Household size	0.088 (0.0164)*	5.40	0.000	0.027
Farm size (Ha)	-0.1760.102)***	-1.73	0.084	0.005
Constant	-1.497(0.291)	-5.14	0.000	
LR chi ² (9)	= 157.87			
Prob > chi2	= 0.000			
Pseudo R2	= 0.700			
Log-likelihood	= -1048.2253			

*, **, *** signifies 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Conclusion

Access to remittance in Nigeria is very low, which may result from little data collected or a lack of proper documentation. From the findings in the study, the following conclusions were deducted: the majority of the household heads were males who were still in their productive age; hence, high livelihood diversification was enhanced by access to remittance. Remittance did not significantly influence poverty due to lack of access to and insufficient data on remittance. The study concludes that more consideration should be given to remittance access and documentation to aid and measure its effect on poverty alleviation.

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Recommendation

It is generally accepted that remittance increases livelihood diversification; hence, it should be encouraged. However, there is no consensus on remittance being able to alleviate poverty or having no influence on household welfare. It is therefore necessary to make some policy recommendations to improve people's living standards through several other approaches such as;

- I. Remittance increases livelihood diversification; hence, remittance should be encouraged with proper documentation of remittance inflows.
- II. Farmers should be provided with larger farm sizes as it increases livelihood diversification and decreasing farm size increases poverty. Therefore, land regulations on the tenure system should be reviewed as this leads to land fragmentation.
- III. Extension agents should ensure education standards are improved by disseminating information on improved and sustainable farm practices and teaching them how to utilise improved inputs and technologies.
- IV. Active membership and participation in cooperative societies should be encouraged as they provide access to credit and education, reducing poverty.
- V. Marketplaces should be provided, central and closer to production locations because increased market distance increases poverty due to additional transportation and other marketing chain costs.

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Declaration of Interest statement

The authors reported no potential conflict of interest.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Distribution of Socioeconomic characteristics of Household heads

Variables	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	
0 – 25	2.31
26 - 35	11.35
36 - 45	27.26
46 - 55	25.62
56 - 65	19.19
65 - 103	14.27
Marital Status	
Married	80.33
Unmarried	19.67
Sex	
Male	87.8
Female	12.2
Household size	
1 – 3	14.03
4 – 6	29.45
7 – 10	40.13
11-29	16.39
Educational level	
Primary	40.07
Secondary	29.27
Tertiary	30.66
Farm size (Ha)	
0 - 0.5	80.45
0.500001 - 1	12.63
1.000 - 10.2986	6.92
Membership of cooperative	
Non - member	96.11
Member	3.89
Access to Credit	
Access	18.96
No Access	81.04
Occupation	
Non – Agriculture	44.9
Agriculture	55.1

Appendix 2: Livelihood Diversification and Poverty by Socioeconomic Characteristics

	Livelihood Diversification Index	
	Poor	Non – Poor
Age (years)		
0 - 25	0.70	0.90
26 - 35	0.75	0.89
36 - 45	0.79	0.84
46 - 55	0.74	0.81
56 - 65	0.74	0.80
65 - 103	0.75	0.71
Marital Status		
Married	0.77	0.83
Unmarried	0.70	0.73
Sex		
Male	0.76	0.84
Female	0.74	0.78
Household size		
1 - 3	0.65	0.72
4 - 6	0.74	0.82
7 - 10	0.78	0.83
11-29	0.87	0.81
Farm size (Ha)		
0 - 0.5	0.74	0.82
0.500001 - 1	0.80	0.77
1.000 - 10.2986	0.78	0.89
Membership of cooperative		
Non – member	0.66	0.79
Member	0.74	0.85
Access to Credit		
Access	0.76	0.82
No Access	0.65	0.80
Occupation		
Non - Agriculture	0.79	0.81
Agriculture	0.73	0.82